

INSTRUCTING READING STRATEGIES RELATED TO THE LEARNERS' LEARNING STYLES

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Annotatsiya: *Ushbu maqola xorijiy tilni o'rganish davomida o'qish kompetensiyasini rivojlantirish va berilgan yozuvli materialni to'liq tushunish hamda turli hildagi o'rganuvchilarning matni o'qish va tushunishda har xil strategiyalarni samarali qo'llash to'g'risida ma'lumotlarni jamlagan.*

Abstract: *This article provides information on the development of reading competence and comprehensive understanding of the given written material while learning a foreign language, and the effective use of different strategies in reading and understanding the text by different types of learners.*

Аннотация: *В данной статье представлена информация о развитии читательской компетенции и всестороннего понимания заданного письменного материала при изучении иностранного языка, а также об эффективном использовании различных стратегий чтения и понимания текста разными типами учащихся.*

Kalit so'zlar: *Chet tillarini o'rganish, o'qish mahorati, o'qish strategiyalari, o'quvchilar turlari, visual o'rganuvchilar, eshitib o'rganuvchilar, kinestetik va og'zaki o'rganuvchilar.*

Key words: *Learning foreign languages, reading skill, reading strategies, types of learners, visual, auditory, kinesthetic, and verbal.*

Ключевые слова: *изучение иностранных языков, навык чтения, стратегии чтения, типы учащихся, визуальные, аудиальные, кинестетические и вербальные.*

Learning foreign languages requires to maintain all four skills of the languages, namely reading, writing, speaking and listening. When a learner is on the threshold of learning a new foreign language, he is supposed to start to learn the alphabet of the selected language due to comprehend the information in written form, this is because reading is the initial part and inseparable process of learning language. Giving a phase to talk about what reading skill is gives us to understand the role of reading in learning a foreign language. Reading is defined as cognitive process that involves decoding symbols to arrive at meaning. Reading is an active process of constructing meaning of the words. Reading skills are abilities that pertain to a person's capacity to read, comprehend, interpret and decode written language and

texts. Reading with a purpose helps the reader to direct information towards a goal and focuses their attention. Although the reasons for reading may vary, the primary purpose of reading is to understand the text. Reading is a thinking process. It allows the reader to use what he or she may already know, also called prior knowledge. During this processing of information, the reader uses strategies to understand what they are reading, uses themes to organize ideas, and uses textual clues to find the meaning of the new words. It is time to talk about reading strategies linking them with the types of learners. This is because different learners use variety of ways to comprehend the written materials. It is necessary to identify the difference among four types of learners in language learning. He four major learning styles are visual, auditory, kinesthetic, and verbal:

1. **Visual:** They often enjoy pictures or visual representations of texts or concepts. They may draw or imagine the scene.
2. **Auditory:** They like to hear the words or concepts. They may listen to the story or read it aloud.
3. **Kinesthetic:** They need different reading strategies as they often need movement. They may walk or pace while reading or listening to a story.
4. **Verbal:** Verbal learners often need to talk about stories. They may also read aloud or ask questions.

It is not right to expect all learners to learn the same way. Even multiple visual learners might have different reading strategies they like to practice to understand the reading more fully. Below there will be provided information about several reading strategies and the types of learners that they might help.

1. **Highlighting the text.** Some students find highlighting the text helpful. Some students will feel nervous about highlighting at first. Others will not know what they need to highlight or why. **This strategy is helpful for visual learners. It may include using different colors and only highlighting key words.**

2. **Annotating the text.** Some students will find that marking the text with notes is most helpful. They might circle key words, underline new vocabulary or confusing words, and star key phrases or details. **This strategy is also helpful for visual learners.** Key things to remember about annotation: a) **every annotation is different;** b) **some students will be uncomfortable.**

3. **Reading aloud.** Some students will love read-aloud time and others will not like it at all. For some students, they need to hear the words spoken. For those students consider these alternatives: a) **having a quiet area where students can whisper the text aloud to themselves;** b) **having auditory books available.**

4. Graphic Organizers. These can be helpful for a variety of **visual** readers. Each organizer works differently. Here are a few and how they may be used: a) **bubble maps**- might be used to tell the main ideas and smaller details; b) **Venn Diagrams**- might be used to tell how things have similar and different traits; c) **KWL charts**– might be used to organize information.

5. Having Questions to think about while reading. This strategy can help **visual, auditory, and verbal** learners alike: a) The visual learner will have something to look for. The auditory learner might listen to questions being asked and think back to what the book is asking; b) the verbal learner gets to talk about the text.

6. Explore the text. This strategy can also help a variety of learners. The learners will look at the text to see if there are keywords listed, titles, headings, pictures, or other clues for the text.

7. Act out the text. For **kinesthetic** learners, acting out dialogue or putting movement to descriptive text can help them retain what they have read.

8. Summarizing. This can be done as both written and oral summarizations. a) **Auditory and verbal learners** will enjoy discussing their summaries. Much of their learning comes from talking through the text. Have them formulate their answers before discussing them. b) **Visual learners** often prefer a graphic organizer or visually appealing document to create summaries or outlines with.

9. Inferring. Students of different learning styles will also like this strategy. Many people make these different strategies, and often they are, but they can certainly be done together. Students will ask questions of the text, especially character motivations or author choices. Then they can look at the text critically to determine what they think the answers might be. They can also use this strategy for prediction. For **Auditory and verbal** readers, they may find a “book club” or partnership set up the best for this type of strategy.

USED BIBLIOGRAPHY:

1. Coffield, F., Moseley, D., Hall, E., Ecclestone, K. (2004). Learning styles and pedagogy in post-16 learning. A systematic and critical review. London: Learning and Skills Research Centre.

2. Pashler, H., McDaniel, M., Rohrer, D., & Bjork, R. (2009). Learning Styles: Concepts and Evidence. Psychological Science in the Public Interest.

3. Hawk, T. F., & Shah, A. J. (2007, January 31). Using Learning Style Instruments to Enhance Student Learning. Decision Sciences: Journal of Innovative Education.

4.Hawk, T. F., & Shah, A. J. (2007, January 31). Using Learning Style Instruments to Enhance Student Learning. Decision Sciences: Journal of Innovative Education.